

EBFMC25-OP-27 · Evaluation of the Relationship Between Cyberchondria Level and eHealth Literacy in Individuals Applying to Polyclinic

 <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.15809041>

Oral Presentation #27 was presented at the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress, held in Ordu, Türkiye, on May 22–24, 2025, and is part of the proceedings titled: Proceedings of the 3rd International Eastern Black Sea Family Medicine Congress.

AUTHORS

Seymanur Ozdemir
<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8420-0159>

Bestegul Coruh Akyol
<https://orcid.org/0000-0002-3555-683X>

AFFILIATIONS

Kumru Community Health Center
Family Medicine
Ordu, Turkey

Ordu University Faculty of Medicine
Department of Family Medicine
Ordu, Turkey

ABSTRACT

Introduction: Cyberchondria is the disruption of functionality by reaching levels that affect the individual's life as a result of negative emotional states and physician applications required as a result of excessive repetition of internet health research (McElroy & Shevlin, 2014). eHealth literacy refers to “the use of emerging information and communication technology to improve or enable health and health care” (Neter & Brainin, 2012). The aim of this study was to determine the levels of cyberchondria and eHealth literacy in individuals over 18 years of age who applied to Ordu University Family Medicine Outpatient Clinic and to determine the relationship between sociodemographic characteristics of patients and cyberchondria and eHealth literacy.

Materials and Methods: This cross-sectional and descriptive study, a questionnaire including the Cyberchondria Severity Scale short form (CSS-12) and the eHealth Literacy Scale was applied together with the sociodemographic data form of the individuals who applied to the Family Medicine Polyclinic. Data were analysed with IBM SPSS V23. Significance level was taken as $p < 0.050$.

Results: The study included 400 participants. 69.5% (n=278) of the participants were between the ages of 18-30 years. The proportion of women was 70.8% (n=283). According to educational status, the highest proportion was university graduates with 67.8% (n=271). In case of any illness/discomfort, the first health institution usually consulted was the family health center with 47.3% (n=189). The mean score of the participants on the e-health literacy scale was 26.71. The mean cyberchondria severity scale score was 28. A statistically weak positive correlation was found between the participants' eHealth Literacy scale score and Cyberchondria Severity Scale score ($p < 0.001$). When the relationship between age and scale scores was examined in our study, a statistically significant difference was observed. The level of cyberchondria and eHealth literacy was found to be higher in those aged between 18-30 years.

Conclusion: The level of cyberchondria and e-health literacy is higher in young people, and this is due to the fact that young people have easier access to the internet and technological devices. The duty of physicians is to educate and raise awareness especially among young people about the adequate and correct use of the internet for health-related information, to identify people who may need help and to make the necessary referrals. In this way, negative consequences such as patient discontinuation of treatment can be prevented and unnecessary health expenditures can be reduced by preventing the patient's repeated visits to health institutions.

PEER REVIEW STATEMENT

This paper has undergone a double-blind peer review process and has been approved by the scientific committee of the conference.

KEYWORDS

Cyberchondria, health literacy, eHealth literacy, health anxiety, hypochondria

CONFLICT OF INTEREST DECLARATION

There is no commercial, financial, or personal conflict of interest in this study.

REFERENCES

McElroy, E., & Shevlin, M. (2014). The development and initial validation of the Cyberchondria Severity Scale (CSS). *Journal of Anxiety Disorders, 28*(2), 259–265.

Neter, E., & Brainin, E. (2012). eHealth literacy: Extending the digital divide to the realm of health information. *Journal of Medical Internet Research, 14*(1), e19.

CORRESPONDING AUTHOR

Seymanur Ozdemir

Kumru Community Health Center

Family Medicine, Ordu, Turkey

<https://orcid.org/0009-0002-8420-0159>

seymanurozdemir52@gmail.com